

Melanin Formation and Break Down of Indole under Udenfriend Condition

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Indole under biomimetic hydroxylation using Udenfriend reaction gives rise to melanin and other products. The results pose a question whether indole could be an alternative substrate for biomelanin.

MELANINS are considered to be derived from the intermediate 5,6-dihydroxy indole by polymerization¹. We have recently found that 3-methyl carbazole under Udenfriend condition (Fe^{2+} /ascorbic acid/EDTA)² undergoes hydroxylation and subsequent dimerization³. So it was of interest to examine

whether indole under Udenfriend condition underwent hydroxylation and subsequent polymerization to yield melanin. The results are reported here.

Materials and Methods: A solution of indole (176 mg in minimum acetone, 2 ml) was added to

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF PROPERTIES OF THE BLACK COMPOUND WITH THAT OF DOPA-MELANIN

Properties	Black compound	DOPA-melanin (Sigma Co.)
1. Solubility	Soluble in 1% alkali. Insoluble in acid and most solvents.	Soluble in 1% alkali. Insoluble in acid and most solvents.
2. Spectra in the visible region	Shape of the curve is similar in both the samples.	Shape of the curve is similar in both the samples.
3. IR (Nujol)	3400, 1640, 1620 cm^{-1}	3400, 1720* 1640, 1620 cm^{-1}
4. Action of alkaline H_2O_2	Decolourisation	Decolourisation

*The only difference is that the DOPA-melanin (Sigma) contains one or two carboxyl groups (1720 cm^{-1}) in its structure.

TABLE 2 - COMPARISON OF THE PROPERTIES OF DEGRADED PRODUCTS WITH THAT OF AUTHENTIC SAMPLE

Compounds	m.p.	Colour with Ehrlich's reagent**	R_f Benzene : Acetone (9 : 1)	UV λ_{max} in $\text{m}\mu$ (log ϵ)	IR ν_{max} in cm^{-1}
1. 3-Hydroxy pyrrole 4,5-dicarboxylic M^{+171}	169°	Faint pink	0.15	252 (2.9)	3400, 1685, 1470, 1385, 1060, 950
2. Isatin	a) 202-3°	Orange	0.20	240 (5.6) 292 (4.0)	3200, 1740, 1760, 1620.
	b) 203-5°	Orange	0.20	240 (5.6) 290 (4.1)	3200, 1740, 1760, 1610.
3. Anthranilic acid	a) 146°	Yellow	0.11	245 (3.56) 322 (3.2)	3500, 3400, 1680, 1620, 1590, 1560.
	b) 145°	Yellow	0.10	245 (3.55) 318 (3.0)	3500, 3400, 1680, 1615, 1600, 1580.
4. 3-Hydroxy anthranilic acid	a) 235-40°	Yellow	0.035	320 (3.5) 252 (3.52)	3400, 1655, 1620, 1550.
	b) 240°	Yellow	0.04	322 (3.57) 252 (3.5)	3400, 1655, 1610, 1550.
5. 5,6-Dihydroxy indole	a) 154-56°	Blue	0.23	222 (4.9) 276 (3.8) 298 (3.75)	The ir could not be obtained due to paucity of the sample.
	b) 156°	Blue	0.24	224 (4.55) 275 (3.7) 298 (3.65)	

a = Degradation product, b = Authentic sample,
** *p*-Dimethyl amino benzaldehyde

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250 ml of 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 6.7. Ascorbic acid (616 mg in water) and EDTA (604.5 mg in water) were added to this solution. The mixture was stirred and a solution of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (90.5 mg) was added dropwise over 15 mins. The whole solution was then stirred at 37° for two hrs in an atmosphere of oxygen. On standing, deposits of black particles, insoluble in acid and all organic solvents were obtained. These were collected by centrifugation (8000 g, 10 mins). On comparison, the properties of the black particles were found to be very similar to those of melanin supplied by Sigma Chemicals Co. (Table 1). Thus the black particles were identified as melanin.

The aqueous solution was then extracted with ether. From the ether layer a brown mass was obtained which on preparative thin layer chromatography [silica gel adsorbent and benzene : acetone (9 : 1) solvent] yielded several compounds. Some of these compounds were isolated and characterised by comparison with authentic samples, Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The results show that under Udenfriend condition indole furnishes 5:6-dihydroxy indole, isatin, melanin, 3-hydroxy anthranilic acid, 3-hydroxy pyrrole-dicarboxylic acid and anthranilic acid.

According to Raper, 5:6-dihydroxy indole is one of the key compounds from which tyrosine-melanin is formed¹. The production of 5:6-dihydroxy indole from indole under Udenfriend condition and subsequent polymerisation to melanin in the present experiment are suggestive that melanin in biological system may directly arise from indole. During this formation some amount of indole is cleaved to 3-hydroxy anthranilic acid and 3-hydroxy pyrrole-dicarboxylic acid. This degradation resembles the degradation of indole or its hydroxylation products by oxidative species similar to dioxygenase system.

It turns out from these results that in hydroxylation of indole under conditions simulating mono-oxygenase

system or mixed function oxidase (Udenfriend reaction) like tyrosinase, some amount of products resembling the products obtained by the action of dioxygenase system (tryptophan pyrrolase) is obtained. The mechanism of monooxygenase reaction like tyrosinase and dioxygenase system like tryptophan pyrrolase has recently been covered by two and four electron oxidation mechanism involving oxenoid species⁴.

It is, therefore, suggestive that the extent of hydroxylation products obtained will depend upon the equilibrium between the action of systems simulating two oxygenase systems. Interestingly, during induced depigmentation in *Bufo melanostictus* or its regeneration, an inverse relationship between tyrosinase and tryptophan pyrrolase has been reported⁵. In other words an equilibrium may be considered to exist *in vivo* and *in vitro* results show a close resemblance so far as the equilibrium between the mono-oxygenase and dioxygenase reactions is concerned.

It may further be pointed out that this is the first report of Udenfriend reaction giving rise to products obtainable from dioxygenase reaction. These results provide an indirect experimental support for the two or four electron oxidation mechanism encompassing the mono-oxygenase and dioxygenase systems.

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